

Psychological Treatment of Indecent Dressing using Self-Instruction Technique

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Abstract

This study is on psychological treatment of indecent dressing using self-instruction technique. It is a psychoanalytical study of a twenty-two year old undergraduate, who was invited by the therapist as a result of her habitual indecent dressing. It was a pre test post test observation study. The treatment strategy was self-instruction technique and skills of rapport, unconditional positive regard, explanation, Socratic dialogue, ego boosting, questioning and assignment. Result obtained showed a remarkable reduction of the level of indecent dressing in the client, from 15 to 7. The follow up was reduced due to great reduction in the level of client's indecent dressing. Based on the result, the researchers recommend that self-instruction technique and skills of rapport among others should be adopted in controlling indecent dressing among young female adults.

Key words: *Psychological, Indecent dressing, Treatment, Behaviour.*

Introduction

Every behaviour is a function of an individual's cognitive and affective processes. Behaviour constitutes the bundle of responses to either internal or external stimuli. An individual's behaviour is often a reflection of his or her character, and can either be developed unconsciously with time, or acquired from external environmental factors. Excess or deficit behaviour are symptomatic, and has causes and effects which impinge on an individual's functioning and the successful functioning of the society. In most cases, the individual's general personality and subsequent self actualization is hampered. In view of the above, this paper treated indecent dressing, a social maladaptive behaviour which indicates immodesty and lack of sense of decency, using the technique of self-instruction and skills of rapport, unconditional positive regard, ego boosting and questioning among others.

Indecent dressing

Indecent dressing is a vice that is practised by all age groups, but common to the youths, especially, the females. Indecent dressing as a social maladaptive behaviour is viewed by Ayeni

(2016) as an improper way of dressing that tends to expose one's body especially the parts that are meant to be covered or private, while Egwim (2010) referred to indecent dressing in a more specific term, as the attitude of someone, male or female that dresses to show off parts of the body such as the breast or buttocks. These twain definitions are evidences that indecent dressing is a social problem.

It is possible to relate to indecent dressing at some point in one's life. Socially, one tends to have the misconception that only youths dresses indecently due to their obsession with youthful exuberance. However, it is necessary to point out that dressing has lost most of its values in our society. Hence, Otubah (2015) asserts that the menace of indecent dressing is gradually becoming a norm and that which African society is known for, is gradually fading away.

Indecent dressing, according to Gbadegbe and Mawuli (2013), is the improper and provocative way of dressing, relative to the society or culture in which it is being perpetrated. Gbadegbe and Mawuli further opined that indecent dressing cannot be properly defined in isolation of the societal norms or religious boundaries. This brings to the fore the assertion of some school of thoughts that indecent dressing is mainly due to 'foreign culture'.

Indecent dressing has symptoms. According to Otubah (2015), the symptoms of indecent dressing include; people seeing nothing wrong in dressing seductively, modelling of top movie stars who dress to complement the roles they play in movies, putting on short skirts, towel-like linen which barely covered their breasts, leaving the rest of the body unattended, wearing of scandal dressing like sagging trousers, show-breast and show belly among others.

However, there are certain factors that cause indecent dressing. According to Antarlaniyan, (2015), indecent dressing is caused by common phrases which are the problems of our generation like 'Only God can judge me, you can't', 'Leave me alone', 'Everyone is entitled to his or her opinion', 'Mind your business' among others. Antarlaniyan further remarked that these phrases have become so common in our society that one can't condemn any wrong doing again because the rewards are usually curses, malice, hatred and condemnation.

Generally, indecent dressing has several consequences. It leads to rape, prostitution, HIV/AIDS and other venereal deadly diseases, lying, armed robbery and poor school grades(Folurunso, 2015). Moreover, Antarlaniyan (2015) noted that indecent dressing is the major cause of various assaults and harassments recorded in the society, overtime. Additionally, Gbadegbe and Mawuli (2013) observed that indecent dressing distracts the attention of both students and lecturers, and that some leakages of examination questions can be attributed to sexual favours as a result of indecent dressing. Also, Toyin (2013) remarked that there is a strong belief among some people that a large number of rape victims were victims of their modes of dressing. Toyin further remarked that as a result of so called 'civilisation', ladies dress half-naked to schools, events and religious gatherings in the name of fashion. Finally, Otubah (2015) remarked that such dressings are highly offensive, and reveals the level of moral decadence in the society.

The need to control indecent dressing becomes imperative in view of its effects and negative consequences. In line with this, (Obegi, 2013) and (Antarlaniyan, 2015) asserted that indecent dressing has been effectively controlled using the following measures; parents dressing decently

and acting as role models to their children, dress codes, mass media, religious institutions and formation of campus brigades.

The client

The client is a twenty-two year old first year student in the university. She habitually dresses indecently as clearly evidenced in her dressing modes. She is the last born, and the only female child in a family of five. She dresses in all manner of short skirts and sleeveless tops, body hugs, spaghetti tops, off shoulder, tight trousers, very short gowns and transparent dresses. The client is always in a company of a group of three girls who are always in similar dressing, and are supposedly her room mates. She is always late for lectures, and despite this, she'll walk straight to the front seat. This caught the researcher's attention who eventually, invited her to her office, for counselling.

Data collected from her mother and family members showed that despite her quiet and innocent look, she is highly indiscriminating, clever and abhors intimidation. However, she talks very little, easily makes friends and can befriend anybody that comes her way. On gaining admission into the university, she secured an apartment in a hostel where there are lots of the so called 'campus babes'. She instantly became friends with two of them such that they reinforced her indecent dressing mode. In their second year, the three friends retained their apartments in the hostel, and continually moved together.

Antecedents, Precedents, Consequences and Contingency

Antecedents: The client from child hood is always in the midst of her brothers. As the only female child she has never really had any close or intimate relationship with girls. She was a day student throughout her secondary education. Most times she was taken to and from school by her parents. Though it was a girls' school, she seldom moved out with class mates and other girls. The family members were never strict about her dressing, especially her mother who pampered her as her only daughter.

Precedents: The social situations associated with her indecent dressing were poor parenting, wrong internet use, fashion, peer pressure and physical attraction, attention seeking, maladaptive thought, inferiority complex and fashion.

Consequences: She imbibes wrong and negative values, loses self-control, self discipline, and easily copies wrong models. She is easily influenced by friends and other's opinions, and carried away by their actions.

Contingency: In view of the antecedents and consequences, the contingencies are noticeable. The therapist therefore desired to assist the client and see that the behaviour is controlled, so that the client will develop into a virtuous young woman of dignity and integrity.

Determination of baseline data

The client was observed for three weeks, in order to find out the level of indecent dressing, before commencement of treatment. This is to enable the therapist make a comparative analysis and determine the impact of the therapy.

Checklist

- Peer pressure
- Fashion

- Wrong internet use
- Attention seeking
- Poor parenting
- Inferiority complex
- Attraction
- Maladaptive thought

The highest score for each item is 3 while the lowest is 1. After the treatment, zero represents absence of the item. This is represented as follows;

3 =highest, 2 = higher, 1 = high, 0 = zero.

Checklist and responses for the first week before treatment

Maintaining stimuli	Occurrences of responses						
	Sun	Mon	Tues	Wed	Thurs	Fri	Sat
Peer pressure	2	3	3	3	2	3	2
Fashion	2	2	2	3	2	2	2
Wrong internet use	2	2	3	2	2	2	1
Attention seeking	3	3	3	2	2	2	2
Attraction	3	3	3	3	3	3	1
Inferiority complex	2	2	2	2	2	3	2
Poor parenting	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
Maladaptive thought	2	2	2	3	3	2	1
TOTAL	18	19	20	20	18	19	13

Average response: 18

Graphical representation of the first week responses before treatment

Second week responses before treatment

Maintaining stimuli	Occurrences of responses						
	Sun	Mon	Tues	Wed	Thurs	Fri	Sat
Peer pressure	1	3	3	2	3	3	3
Fashion	2	3	2	2	2	2	2
Wrong internet use	1	2	2	2	2	2	2
Attention seeking	1	2	2	2	2	2	2
Attraction	1	3	3	3	3	3	3
Inferiority complex	1	3	2	3	3	3	2
Poor parenting	1	2	1	1	2	2	1
Maladaptive thought	2	2	2	3	3	3	3
TOTAL	10	20	17	18	20	20	18

Average response: 17

Graphical representation of the second week responses before treatment

Third week responses before treatment

Maintaining stimuli	Occurrences of responses						
	Sun	Mon	Tues	Wed	Thurs	Fri	Sat
Peer pressure	2	3	3	3	2	3	2
Fashion	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
Wrong internet use	1	2	2	2	2	2	2
Attention seeking	2	2	2	2	3	2	2
Attraction	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
Inferiority complex	2	3	2	3	3	3	3
Poor parenting	1	2	1	1	2	2	2
Maladaptive thought	1	3	2	3	3	3	2
TOTAL	15	20	17	19	20	20	17

Average response: 18

Graphical representation of the third week responses before treatment

The average baseline data for the three weeks observation is $54/3= 18$

The therapist noticed that the major contributing factors were poor parenting, peer pressure, inferiority complex, fashion and maladaptive thought.

Therapeutic goals

The therapist:

-To have a sense of satisfaction and fulfilment for a job well done

The client

-To develop a sense of modesty and decency in her dressing.

-To cultivate self control and self discipline.

- To have the ego boosted and self-esteem increased
- To believe in herself, and develop self confidence.

Strategy and treatment procedure

Theory: The therapeutic treatment used by the therapist is based on Skinner's Operant conditioning theory of behaviour modification. Mostly, human behaviours are naturally operant, and behaviour modification is the application of operant learning principles in changing behaviour (Abodike, Nwankwo & Ugwuegbu, 2014).

Techniques and skills: The major technique was self-instruction. This technique is based on the principle of self regulation or independent learning. Independent learning implies doing it alone, unaided (Knight, 1996). Thus, it helps individuals become independent learners, by gaining the skills. The treatment skills used were rapport, unconditional positive regard, Socratic dialogue, questioning, ego boosting, explanation, encouragement and assignment.

First week

Self-instruction was used so as to inculcate self talk through role playing and rehearsal. The client was sensitized on the negative effects of indecent dressing, and encouraged to use this positive statement 'I must dress modestly and decently in order to maintain my dignity and integrity, and develop into a virtuous young woman'. She was informed that her admission into the university indicates her intelligence and capacity for self actualization, while her stay in the university is for total transformation. Therefore, she should avoid indecent dressing in all its ramifications. She was engaged in a dialogue which revealed some of her inconveniences and negative experiences in her indecent wears, such as; difficulty in movement, negative sexual remarks from males and scandalous remarks from some people. She was taught to develop a sense of decency in her dressing because the fact that a lot of people dress in all manner of immodest clothes does not make them fashionable, attractive and acceptable.

Rapport was used to show a sense of humour, involvement before, after, inside or outside the clinic, encouraging discussion and showing interest in the client as well as sharing personal insights and experiences. Unconditional positive regard was used to show respect for the client, to express non-judgemental and impartial, value and accept her as unique, express compassion and understanding of her struggles with life challenges. This is because indecent dressing can result from ignorance. Explanation was used to describe to her, the benefits of decency and modesty in dressing, and to help her develop logical thinking as well as guide her judgement. Ego boosting was used to make her feel better and comfortable in modest and decent wears. Finally, assignment was given to her to say the positive statement ten times, every morning before getting ready to leave the hostel, and before retiring to bed, at night. This is for cognitive, affective and behavioural integration of her personality.

The therapist engaged the services of an assistant who lives in the same hostel with the client, and is always modestly and decently dressed. The client seeing the researcher as congruent, believed in her, accepted and developed interest in the treatment, as such accepted the assistant

to observe her dressing in the hostel and on campus. The assistant is to praise her any time she dresses decently to go for lectures and attend other activities in the campus.

Checklist and responses for first week after treatment

Maintaining stimuli	Occurrences of responses						
	Sun	Mon	Tues	Wed	Thurs	Fri	Sat
Peer pressure	1	1	2	1	1	1	2
Fashion	1	1	1	2	2	1	1
Wrong internet use	1	1	1	1	2	1	2
Attention seeking	1	2	1	1	1	1	1
Attraction	2	2	2	1	1	2	2
Inferiority complex	1	1	2	1	1	1	1
Poor parenting	1	1	1	1	2	1	2
Maladaptive thought	1	1	2	1	1	1	2
TOTAL	9	10	12	9	11	10	13

Average response: 11

Graphical representation of first week responses after treatment

From the responses, it can be observed that there was a marked reduction in indecent dressing. The client was able to reduce her inferiority complex, maladaptive thought and attention seeking. The researcher reemphasized on the use of the positive statement 'I must dress modestly and decently at all times, in order to maintain my dignity and integrity, and develop into a virtuous young lady'. She dresses smartly and simply, both in the hostel and campus. The research assistant, her friend reinforced her with praise. Her performance in the clinic earned her a novel.

Maintaining stimuli	Occurrences of responses						
	Sun	Mon	Tues	Wed	Thurs	Fri	Sat
Peer pressure	1	1	1	1	0	1	0
Fashion	1	1	1	2	0	0	1
Wrong internet use	0	1	1	0	1	1	1
Attention seeking	0	0	1	0	1	1	1
Attraction	1	1	1	0	0	1	1
Inferiority complex	1	1	0	1	1	1	0
Poor parenting	0	0	0	1	1	1	1
Maladaptive thought	1	1	1	1	0	1	0
TOTAL	5	6	6	6	4	7	5

Average response: 6

Graphical representation of second week responses after treatment

From the responses one can observe a remarkable improvement in the client's ability to develop sense of decency, and have her ego boosted. The assistant reinforced her with more praise and she was really out to prove her sense of decency, She maintained her focus on the treatment. The researcher informed her that she does not have to dress half naked in order to be beautiful and attractive. The therapist also advised her to dress decently to every occasion. She was observed for the third week and her responses recorded as shown.

Response for third week after treatment

Maintaining stimuli	Occurrences of responses						
	Sun	Mon	Tues	Wed	Thurs	Fri	Sat
Peer pressure	0	1	1	0	0	0	1
Fashion	1	0	0	1	1	1	1
Wrong internet use	1	0	0	0	0	1	0
Attention seeking	1	1	1	1	0	0	1
Attraction	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
Inferiority complex	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
Poor parenting	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
Maladaptive thought	0	1	0	1	1	0	1
TOTAL	3	3	3	3	4	3	6

Average response: 4

Graphical representation of the responses for third week after treatment.

From the table, one can observe that the responses on Saturdays tend to persist. Also, fashion, attention seeking and maladaptive thought still need to come down. This, according to the client results from the need to dress in all forms of party wears for the weekend.

Nevertheless, the client showed great improvement, indicative of her zeal to develop into a young decent lady of dignity and integrity. She was reinforced with praise by her friend, the research assistant, and a big notebook and a biro from the researcher. The therapist was confident that she will not relapse, consequent of the evidenced effort she put in during the treatment sessions.

Result

Average response for the three weeks after treatment

First week responses=11

Second week responses=6

Third week responses=4

$$21/3=7$$

Discussion

The result shows that there is a remarkable reduction in the level of the client's indecent dressing. In the first week during treatment, the level reduced from 15 prior to treatment, to 11, and in the second week, it reduced further to 6, and finally to 4 in the last week. The entire treatment reduced the level of indecent dressing from 15 to 7. This indicates that self-instruction technique and skills of rapport, unconditional positive regard, Socratic dialogue, ego boosting and explanation are effective in controlling indecent dressing in a client.

Treatment for indecent dressing could be self-regulated because self-oriented therapies are characterised by a very great effort on the part of the client. Client take responsibility for the elimination of the undesirable behaviour. Using a positive statement to control an undesirable behaviour, after learning and understanding about oneself and the behaviour is capable of controlling an individual's undesirable behaviour pattern. The result of this study is in line with the findings of Nwankwo and Obi(2014) which asserts that self-instruction is capable of eliminating an individual's undesirable behaviour pattern.

Follow-up

The frequency of follow up was reduced due to the remarkable decline in the level of client's indecent dressing as a result of the treatment.

Implication

From the result of the study, it is observed that the technique of self-instruction and skills of rapport, unconditional positive regard, questioning, ego boosting and explanation are useful in controlling indecent dressing in young female adult.

Conclusion

This study proves that self-instruction, rapport, unconditional positive regard, explanation, ego boosting, encouragement, assignment were useful in controlling indecent dressing.

Recommendation

The techniques and skills of this study should be employed by Guidance counsellors in controlling indecent dressing in young female adults.

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